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ENTITIES COMBATING ILLEGAL DRUG TRAFFICKING

ANNOTATION

The article analyzes the theoretical and methodological foundations of studying such a social problem as drug trafficking; it examines the role and causes of the spread of drugs, including medicinal ones, in the life of human society, which have been widely and legally used and continue to be used in all parts of the globe.

Bundan tashqari, ushbu bobda narkotik moddalarning noqonuniy aylanishiga qarshi kurashning sub'ektlari va huquqiy asoslari belgilab berilgan. Xalqaro narkotik savdosi uzoq tarixga ega. BMT tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashning umumiy tamoyillari ko'rib chiqiladi. Jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashning tarixiy tajribasi tahlil qilingan.

Key words: UN, INCB, CND, ECOSOC, UNDCP Interpol, transnational crime, illegal trafficking in narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and precursors, areas of international cooperation, measures to combat, control measures.

GIYOHVANDLIK VOSITALARNING NOQONUNIY MUOMILASIGA QARSHI KURASHISH SUB'EKTLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada giyohvandlik vositalarning noqonuniy muomilasi kabi ijtimoiy muammoni o'rganishning nazariy va uslubiy asoslari tahlil qilingan. Butun dunyoda keng va qonuniy ravishda qo'llanilgan va hozirda ham qo'llanilayotgan giyohvandlik vositalarining hamda dori vositalarning inson hayotidagi o'rni va tarqalishi sabablari o'rganilgan.

Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqolada giyohvandlik vositalarning noqonuniy aylanishiga qarshi kurashish subyektlari va huquqiy asoslari belgilab berilgan. Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashning umumiy tamoyillari ko'rib chiqilgan. Jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashning tarixiy tajribasi tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: BMT, INCB, CND, ECOSOC, UNDCP Interpol, transmilliy jinoyatchilik, giyohvandlik vositalari, psixotrop moddalar va prekursorlarning noqonuniy aylanishi, xalqaro hamkorlik sohalari, qarshi choralar, nazorat choralar.

СУБЪЕКТЫ БОРЬБЫ С НЕЗАКОННЫМ ОБОРОТОМ НАРКОТИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье проводится анализ теоретико-методологических основ изучения такой социальной проблемы как оборот наркотических средств. Исследуется роль и причины распространения наркотиков, в том числе и лекарственных, в жизни человеческого общества, которые широко и легально использовались и продолжают использоваться во всех частях земного шара.

Кроме того, в данной главе указаны субъекты и правовые основы борьбы с незаконным оборотом наркотиков. Международная торговля наркотиками имеет долгую историю. Рассматриваются общие принципы борьбы с преступностью, выработанные ООН. Анализируется исторический опыт противодействия преступности.

Ключевые слова: ООН, МККН, КНС, ЭКОСОС, ЮНДКП Интерпол, транснациональное преступление, незаконный оборот наркотических средств, психотропных веществ и прекурсоров, направления международного сотрудничества, меры борьбы, меры контроля.

Currently, within the framework of legal regulation of the fight against illegal drug trafficking, the issue of subjects of the fight is relevant. And this is due to the fact that the study of subjects allows us to clearly outline the circle of participants in the fight against illegal drug trafficking, as well as to identify their place and role in this area, determine their competence, powers, and influence on the drug situation as a whole.

The subject of the fight against illegal drug trafficking can be defined as an independent participant in international, political relations, having certain rights and bearing certain obligations provided for it by an international treaty.

The most active participants in the fight against illegal drug trafficking are two groups of subjects - states and international organizations.

Thus, the state acts as a subject of the fight in the following two forms:

- government as a whole;
- state bodies.

Governments of states act as subjects primarily as participants in international law-making. This is evident in the fact that it is precisely at the intergovernmental level that the majority of international treaties and agreements establishing general principles of relations between subjects in matters of combating drug trafficking have been concluded and are currently being concluded.

State bodies, in turn, act as subjects in cases where their participation is directly provided for in international normative legal acts concluded at the intergovernmental level. They can also act as subjects in two forms: as subjects of lawmaking and as subjects of law enforcement.

In addition, state bodies act as subjects of the fight against illegal drug trafficking in cases expressly stipulated in the international intergovernmental treaties concluded on The question of the list of state bodies that are subjects of the fight against illegal drug trafficking is not exhaustive.

International treaties and agreements often reflect a list of state authorities of the relevant states parties to the treaty.

For example, according to Article 5 of the Agreement between the Member States of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization on Cooperation in Combating Illicit Trafficking in Narcotic Drugs, Psychotropic Substances and Their Precursors of 2004, cooperation is carried out through direct contacts between central competent authorities [1].

Such bodies are:

- ministries of foreign affairs;
- departments for control over the circulation of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances;
- prosecutor general's offices (prosecutor's offices);
- ministries of internal affairs (public security);
- national security agencies and special services;
- border agencies;
- customs agencies;
- ministries of justice;
- ministries of health;
- ministries of education;
- and other agencies.

All the above-mentioned state bodies perform functions to prevent illegal drug trafficking. In particular, the competence of the ministries of foreign affairs includes control over the fulfillment of international obligations by states arising from issues of combating illegal drug trafficking.

The functions of the prosecutor's office include the suppression of drug trafficking channels, the activities of criminal groups involved in drug smuggling and maintaining drug dens. The state departments for control over the circulation of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, in turn, are engaged in the development of state policy, control and supervision in the field of drugs, etc.

Thus, the above list of central bodies is not exhaustive, since, by agreement of the parties, it may also include other bodies and departments, "whose functions include issues of implementation of this Agreement".

The next important subject in the fight against illegal drug trafficking is international organizations. International organizations whose competence includes drug issues are heterogeneous in their number, goals, and areas of activity set out in their founding documents.

By concluding treaties with states in accordance with the provisions of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties between States or between International Organizations of 1986, they do not exercise their own will, but exercise the powers granted to them by the charter [2].

By the beginning of the 21st century, a completely clear system of international intergovernmental organizations had been formed that controlled the use and distribution of drugs, as well as the suppression of illegal activities in these areas.

The basis of the current system of international organizations for the control of the production, movement and use of drugs is the United Nations and its specialized agencies. Here, first of all, it is necessary to name the UN Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) Commission on Drugs, the International Narcotics Control Board (INCB) and the UN International Drug Control Programme (UNDCP).

ECOSOC is the principal organ of the United Nations for coordinating economic and social activities and specialized agencies and institutions. One of the six functional commissions of ECOSOC is the Commission on Narcotic Drugs (CND).

It is one of the main bodies in the UN system responsible for developing and implementing policies on all issues related to illicit drug trafficking. The Commission reviews the functioning of the drug control system, examines the need for modifications to it, and makes recommendations on scientific research into drugs.

In addition, its function is to prepare new international normative legal acts and actively work to improve existing documents and to develop drafts of new documents. An equally important task of the commission on narcotic drugs is to establish a list of narcotic drugs subject to control.

The second specialized body to combat illicit drug trafficking is the International Narcotics Control Board (INCB), which also works under the guidance of ECOSOC as an information, monitoring and advisory body. INCB is the successor to the drug control bodies, the first of which was established by international treaty more than 70 years ago.

The treaties impose a number of specific responsibilities on the Committee. In accordance with Article 9 of the Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs of 1961, the Committee "shall endeavour to limit the cultivation, production, manufacture and use of drugs to the quantities required for medical and scientific purposes, to ensure their availability for such purposes and to prevent illicit cultivation, production, manufacture and use of drugs and illicit trafficking in drugs" [3].

The tasks of the INCB also include:

- monitoring compliance with the treaties on narcotic drugs;
- inquiring from states about the annual production, consumption, import and export of drugs;
- monitoring the drug trade;
- making recommendations to countries to suspend the import of narcotic substances into a particular country, etc.

In carrying out its duties, the Committee shall cooperate with the governments of States and maintain a continuous dialogue with them in order to promote the achievement of the objectives of the treaties. This dialogue shall be carried out through systematic consultations and special missions organised by agreement with the governments concerned.

INCB cooperates with UNDCP, of which its secretariat forms part, and with other international organizations concerned with drug control matters, including, in addition to ECOSOC and its Commission on Narcotics, the relevant specialized agencies of the United Nations, in particular WHO.

In accordance with the international drug control agreements, the Committee is required to submit an annual report to the ECOSOC Commission on its work, which provides an analysis of the drug control situation worldwide.

That governments are kept informed of existing and potential situations that may jeopardize the achievement of the objectives of the Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs of 1961, the Convention on Psychotropic Substances of 1971 and the United Nations Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances of 1988.

The Committee draws the attention of governments to gaps and shortcomings in national control systems and in the implementation of treaty obligations, and makes proposals and recommendations aimed at improving the situation at both the national and international levels.

The next main subject of international control is the United Nations Drug Control Programme (UNDCP), created in accordance with UN General Assembly Resolution No. 45/179 of December 29, 1990. This body united the structures and functions of all previous UN drug control bodies - the Department of Narcotics, the UN Fund for Drug Abuse Control and International Secretariat of the International Narcotics Control Board. UNDCP, like the International Board, is based in Vienna. UNDCP has been entrusted with the sole responsibility for coordinating and directing all UN drug control activities.

UNDCP offers the review an assessment of drug control legislation and practice, advice on administrative and legal issues related to the implementation of international conventions, provision of specialist consultants for the development of national plans to combat illicit drug trafficking, relevant draft laws, assistance in training judges, prosecutors, investigators and other officials implementing the new laws.

In addition to the UNDCP, other UN organizations involved in drug control include the World Health Organization, the International Labor Organization, and the UN Crime Prevention Division, which studies the links between crime and drug trafficking, including issues of drug money laundering.

The International Narcotics Control Board and the United Nations International Drug Control Programme cooperate closely with organizations outside the United Nations system, especially the International Criminal Police Organization (Interpol) and the Customs Co-operation Council, also known as the World Customs Organization.

The International Criminal Police Organization – Interpol was created in 1923. According to Article 2 of the Interpol Charter, in force since 1956, the main objectives of its activities are:

1. Ensuring the interaction of all criminal police agencies within the framework of the existing legislation of the country and in the spirit of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights;
2. The creation and development of institutions that can successfully contribute to the prevention and fight against criminal offences [4].

Interpol currently includes 192 countries (Afghanistan, Belgium, China, Denmark, Finland, Ireland, Italy, Serbia, Russia, France and other states) [5].

Interpol's criminal intelligence focuses on the most commonly used drugs in illegal drug trafficking - cannabis, cocaine, heroin, synthetic drugs. Interpol's primary tasks in relation to drugs are:

1. Identifying new trends in illegal drug trafficking and criminal organizations operating internationally;
2. Assistance to national and international law enforcement agencies involved in combating illicit drug production, trafficking and abuse, namely:
 - collection and analysis of intelligence data from Member States and dissemination of this information to other countries;
 - support for international drug research by organizing operational meetings of experts;
 - assistance in drug investigations involving at least two member countries;
 - organization of operational negotiations of Interpol members, at which the main directions of the fight against drugs are approved;
 - organization of conferences on specific issues related to drugs, for example, exchange of information on the latest methods of investigation and strengthening of cooperation, etc.

Since 1930, Interpol has had a separate division dealing with the drug problem. It maintains a database containing all information related to drugs with a card index of drug dealers.

In addition, its responsibilities include expanding cooperation between national anti-drug agencies and services and improving the exchange of information between all countries on issues related to illicit drug trafficking, strengthening the capabilities of national services in controlling illicit drug trafficking.

The NCB Interpol compiles, in accordance with the established form, and sends to the General Secretariat of Interpol information on the status and structure of crime, on persons who are members of organized criminal groups, as well as on persons who have committed crimes related to terrorism, illegal trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, the production and sale of counterfeit money, with an encroachment on historical and cultural values, and other crimes that, in accordance with the mandatory decisions of the General Assembly of Interpol, are subject to inclusion in international criminal statistics. At the same time, the transfer of information, the dissemination of which may cause damage to the security of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is not allowed.

All these and a number of other interested organizations (FAO, UNIDO, UNICEF, UNESCO) meet annually to discuss the problems of coordinating drug control work within the UN. Regional international organizations, unlike the United Nations, solve local problems that arise in the fight against illegal drug trafficking. The Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) occupies a special place.

The SCO is a regional international organization founded in 2001 and whose member countries are China, Russia, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan.

In accordance with Article 1 of the founding document of the SCO - the Charter of June 7, 2002, the main goals and objectives of the SCO are:

1. joint counteraction to the fight against illegal drug trafficking;
2. joint search for solutions to problems that will arise in the 21st century, etc. [6].

Also among the regional international associations dealing with the problems of illegal drug trafficking, the following unions of states can be named:

- Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS);
- South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC);
- Inter-American Drug Abuse Control Commission (CICAD);
- Southern African Development Community (SADC);

- African Union (AU). In 1975, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) was created, which is a regional union of West African countries, the member countries of which are Gambia, Guinea, Liberia, Mali, Nigeria and other states.

One of the goals of ECOWAS is to combat crime and illegal drug trafficking, and to ensure peace and security in hot spots (Liberia, Guinea-Bissau). The South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) is an economic and political organization of eight countries in South Asia (Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka), formed in 1985.

One of the areas of SAARC activity is the security aspect, the fight against illegal trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, as well as the adoption of normative legal acts.

In 1988, the Inter-American Commission against Drug Abuse (CICAD) was established. CICAD's activities are developing in the following main areas of cooperation:

- exchange of data on the scale of drug trafficking;
- the state of the system for monitoring the situation with illegal drug trafficking;
- development of educational prevention programs for schoolchildren;
- conducting propaganda campaigns in the media;
- mobilization of public support for the fight against illegal drug trafficking;
- exchange of experience between national legislative bodies and creation of effective mechanisms of cooperation;

- development and implementation of measures to regulate the movement of precursors and chemicals in the region. CICAD helps the Central American republics modernize and coordinate drug control laws.

The Southern African Development Community (SADC) is a trade and economic union of the countries of Southern Africa, created in 1992. The participating countries are South Africa, Namibia, Angola, etc. The goals of SADC also include maintaining peace and security, implementing certain measures regarding drugs, etc.

The African Union (AU) is an international intergovernmental organization uniting 54 African states (Algeria, Guinea, Egypt, Kenya, Tunisia), and is the successor to the Organization of African Unity (OAU).

This organization was founded in 2002. According to the Constitutive Act of the African Union, the goals of the organization are: promoting international cooperation in accordance with the UN Charter, strengthening peace, security and stability on the continent, etc.

Special attention should be paid to international non-governmental organizations in the process of combating illegal drug trafficking. Currently, more than 20 non-governmental international organizations operate in various regions of the world, the purpose of which is to assist government agencies of the relevant countries in combating drug trafficking, rehabilitating drug addicts, etc.

Among such organizations are the International Association against Drug Abuse and Drug Trafficking (Moscow, Russia), the International Committee of Non-Governmental Organizations on Drugs (Vienna, Austria), Vienna Committee of Non-Governmental Organizations on Drugs, International Council on Alcoholism and Drug Abuse (Lausanne, Italy), International Federation of Non-Governmental Organizations for the Prevention of Drug Abuse (Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia), etc.

The activities of these associations are carried out on the basis and within the framework of their own charters. International non-governmental organizations cover a large number of countries with their activities, developing this activity in the direction of expanding the territories of coverage. Summarizing the above, today in the world there is a holistic system of subjects of the fight against illegal drug trafficking.

But the States and the United Nations, represented by its specialized bodies, remain the most important actors. Despite the fact that there are various actors in the fight against illicit drug trafficking, this problem requires a coordinated approach, which is possible only on the basis of certain basic principles. Such basic principles are reflected in such international normative acts as the Charter of the United Nations [7].

The Declaration on Principles of International Law concerning Friendly Relations and Cooperation between States in accordance with the Charter of the United Nations of 1970, the Final Act of the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe of 1975 [8], the Declaration of Principles Governing Relations between the member States of the Conference on Interaction and Confidence-building Measures in Asia and other normative acts.

The commitment of the international community to the principles stipulated by the UN Charter in their understanding was confirmed in the UN Millennium Declaration of September 8, 2000. Article 2 of the Declaration reads as follows: "We reiterate our commitment to the purposes and principles of the Charter of the United Nations, which have proven timeless and universal"[9].

In addition, the relevance of the principles is increasing as States and peoples become more and more interconnected. The following three general principles occupy a special place in the field of drug trafficking regulation:

- the principle of State cooperation;
- the principle of non-interference in matters within the internal jurisdiction of the State;
- the principle of conscientious fulfillment of obligations under international law.

So, the first general principle is the principle of cooperation. The principle of State cooperation is enshrined not only in Paragraph 5 of Article 2 of the Charter of the United Nations, but also in the Declaration on Principles of International Law Concerning Friendly Relations and Cooperation between States in Accordance with the Charter of the United Nations.

According to the 1970 Declaration, the principle of cooperation obliges States to "cooperate with each other, regardless of differences in their political, economic and social systems, in various fields of international relations in order to maintain international peace and security and promote international economic stability and progress, the common well-being of peoples and international cooperation...." [10].

This principle is particularly important in the field of the international fight against drug trafficking, since only joint active actions by States contribute to a more effective fight against drug trafficking than actions by States individually.

The next principle is that of the duty not to interfere in matters within the domestic jurisdiction of the State. This principle is enshrined in Article 2 of the UN Charter, the Declaration on Principles of International Law Concerning Friendly Relations and Cooperation between States in accordance with the UN Charter, the Final Act of the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe, and others.

Thus, according to Paragraph 7 of Article 2 of the UN Charter, "The Charter does not give the United Nations the right to interfere in matters that are essentially within the internal jurisdiction of any state ...". According to the Declaration on Principles of International Law, "no State or group of States has the right to interfere, directly or indirectly, for whatever reason, in the internal and external affairs of any other State".

Summarizing the two provisions of the above-mentioned normative acts, the principle of non-interference means that States or groups of States refrain from any direct or indirect interference in matters that fall within the competence of another State. In addition, States have an inalienable right to choose a political system without interference from another State.

The principle of non-interference in internal affairs plays an important role in the fight against drug trafficking, since the activities of States related to the fight against drug trafficking include not only the establishment of obligations for States, the principles of their activities, but also the opportunity to independently determine and specify methods, forms, and directions of combating drug trafficking in their territory. territories.

And the third basic principle, enshrined in Article 2 of the UN Charter and in the Declaration on Principles of International Law Concerning Friendly Relations and Cooperation between States in accordance with the UN Charter, is the principle of conscientious fulfillment of international obligations. According to paragraph 2 of Article 2 of the Charter of the United Nations, "all Members of the United Nations faithfully fulfill their obligations under this Charter ...".

Thus, the principle of conscientious fulfillment of obligations by States implies that States must faithfully fulfill their obligations assumed in accordance with the UN Charter, as well as those arising from generally recognized principles, as well as from existing international treaties. This principle is also important, since unfair compliance with the requirements of international treaties and their obligations can significantly reduce the effectiveness of efforts to combat drug trafficking.

Above, three basic general principles were discussed regarding cooperation between States in the field of combating drug trafficking and regulation. However, there are international legal acts that establish certain special principles of cooperation between States in the field of combating drug trafficking. One of these documents is the 1998 United Nations Declaration on the Guiding Principles of Drug Demand Reduction.

The objectives of this Declaration are to allocate funds for the implementation of demand reduction programmes, as well as to take balanced measures to promote interregional and international cooperation in order to control the supply and reduce demand for drugs and psychotropic substances. The Declaration contains guidelines that define "the development of a demand reduction component in national and international drug control strategies ..." [11].

The United Nations Declaration on the Guiding Principles of Drug Demand Reduction contains the following principles:

- respect for the sovereignty and territorial integrity of States;
- respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms and the principles of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights;
- the principle of joint ownership.

In addition, "a balanced approach should be taken to implement mutually reinforcing measures to reduce demand and supply within the framework of an integrated approach to solving the drug problem."

According to the 1998 UN Declaration on the Guiding Principles of Drug Demand Reduction, these principles should be implemented within the framework of special international programs, which, being funded by all interested parties, should be implemented on the territory of all participating countries [12].

The Declaration devotes a special place to issues of cooperation between States in the implementation of the principles of drug demand reduction. Namely, a partnership approach to solving a problem is important for identifying effective methods of solving it, for developing and implementing appropriate policies and programs.

So, the United Nations Declaration on the Guiding Principles of Drug Demand Reduction is a fairly comprehensive document that sets out the guiding principles of cooperation, how to implement them, the obligations of the United Nations Member States, as well as measures to solve problems.

As a result of the study of participants in the fight against drug trafficking, a range of subjects has been identified, which include States and their bodies, international organizations, and regional organizations, as well as their place and role in this area. In addition, the principles of drug demand reduction are analyzed.

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